

Article Title:
**Impact of Violence on the Professional Commitments of Journalists in
Pakistan**

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of violence on the professional commitments of Pakistani journalists and tried to find out the reasons for violence and its impact on their professional commitments in Pakistan. Pakistan has been considered one of the most dangerous countries in the World for journalists. A libertarian theory of press to support the study has been applied. The survey method is used to collect the data from journalists. Working journalists from different media groups in Lahore were considered the population. The sample size for the study is 200 journalists from Lahore. The study explores the reasons for violence against Pakistani journalists and the relationship between freedom of expression and violence. The results showed that freedom of expression is not the main reason for violence against journalists. There are several reasons for violent acts against journalists, including lack of justice, blackmailing, personal interests, pressure from other sources, etc. Results also indicated that journalists are living in fear of violence, which may compel them to self-censor, impacting their credibility with readers.

Keywords: *Violence, Journalists, Professional Commitment, Self-Censorship, Pressure Groups.*

Introduction

Media reflects certain societal facades, which inevitably require a projection, not only for realism but also for the promotion of certain psycho-social happenings, in the context of present order within time and space, having a consciousness of the sequential past, linking with the present, and projecting cause and effect for future possibilities. The public has the right to be familiar with the surroundings, and it is the responsibility of journalists to update them. World Press Freedom Day is celebrated on the 3rd of May every year since 1993 to establish and sustain an autonomous free press for the maturity and continuation of democracy. Pakistan is one of those unsafe countries where journalists face constraints on a regular basis, particularly after becoming partners in the war on terror. According to the Press Freedom Index (2015) of Reporters sans frontières (RSF), out of 180 countries, Pakistan's position was 159. Since 1992, 57 journalists have been killed in Pakistan, according to the Committee to Protect Journalists (CPJ). There is a huge list of media workers who have suffered pain, enforced disappearances, harassment, captivity, illogical confinement, and terrorization from the administration and non-state actors.

The UNESCO Director-General's Report 2014 on the Protection of Media Workers and the Threat of Impunity gives an analysis of the ill-treatment of journalists all over the world. It covers the period from January 2006 to December 2013.

In Pakistan, the situation for journalists is even more terrible in terms of expressions of freedom of thought and the right to inform the public about reality. Pakistan's media community is effectively under siege. Journalists, in particular those covering national security issues or human rights, are targeted from all sides in a disturbing pattern of abuses carried out to silence their reporting. The constant threat puts journalists in an impossible position, where virtually any sensitive story leaves them at risk of violence from one side or another. Most of the media workers were slain and hurt in connection with their work. Zaman Mehsud was murdered in Tank on November 3. The Tehrik e Taliban Pakistan (TTP) claimed responsibility for the assault, saying it was just because of his news reports against them. TTP divisions have warned journalists of harsh results if they do not give them exposure to the media.

Pakistan is a country where people of different religious beliefs and affiliations, with sects, races, and diverse ideologies, live. There are fundamental religious parties and democratic parties too, and they have their armed wings, which they do not recognise publicly. Every time a journalist comes up with an exploratory and exclusive story that discloses the foundation of one of these authorities, he suffers psychological and physical pain. Being an ally of three insurgencies, many areas of Pakistan have become similar to war zones. A lot of journalists functioning in these zones – in tribal areas, the North West of Baluchistan, and Karachi – have been enforced to keep quiet, and their news experiences self-censorship, according to a Pakistani journalist (Rashid, March 29, 2019).

This study aims to explore the reasons for violence against Pakistani journalists and the relationship between freedom of expression and violence. Pakistan is considered the most hazardous country in the world by international media watchdogs in terms of freedom of expression and protection of journalists. It is significant to point out here that brutal attacks on journalists are mounting day by day in different areas of the country and from different stakeholders.

This study analyses the relationship between freedom of expression and violence and the impact of violence on the professional commitments of Pakistani journalists and observes the impact of news of violence, terrorization, killings, kidnappings, injuries, etc. on the journalistic duties and the commitment of journalists to their duties. Pakistan is considered one of the central countries of the world from different perspectives, and the media as well as journalists are morally bound to perform their duties in an objective way to keep the nation informed about the current situation.

Objectives of the study

1. To investigate the causes of violence against journalists in Pakistan
2. To investigate the relationship between journalists' freedom of expression and violence against

them.

3. To determine whether or how violence affects Pakistani journalists' ability to do their duties.

Literature Review

Gohdes et al. (2017) have highlighted the insecurities of governments across the globe regarding the free press, highlighted the issue of the killing of journalists all over the world, and revealed that state and non-state actors are involved in targeting journalists when they see that the news stories are against their policies. The results show that most of the time, local journalists were killed, and the culprits have remained unrecognised. The research has also highlighted that instead of serious crimes against media persons, there were all other forms of crimes being committed against them, including torture, kidnapping, imprisonment, and intimidation multiple times. Aslam (2015) examined the fact that the basic right of freedom of expression for media workers in Pakistan is being threatened both by the state and non-state actors, and they are facing an issue that is compounded by the risk to their safety and survival. She highlighted some cases to reveal how journalistic investigations led to them being harassed, kidnapped, tortured, and even killed. She highlighted the stories of three Pakistani journalists, Hayat Ullah Khan, Saleem Shahzad, and Umar Cheema, to draw the attention of the whole world towards the deteriorating situation of freedom of the press in Pakistan and the hurdles faced by the press community there.

Steadman (2015) highlighted the need for providing legal and all other types of protection to international journalists, as they are the most vulnerable and easy targets in other countries. Smyth (2013) discussed all rules and regulations for media as ordered by the rulers during the previous five wars, including World War 1, World War 2, the Korean War, the Vietnam War, and the Persian Gulf War. The research analysed different trends in all five wars, various types of rules and censorship imposed on US journalists, and how trends were set to control the flow of information.

Tejeci (2015) examined the condition of Journalists in Kosovo to unveil the actual conditions of pressures and influences on media organisations and their workers. The responses from the questionnaires show that the impact on the journalist is greater than the peripheral perception. Feinstein et al. (2016) examined the condition of Iranian journalists and argued that all the media watchdogs, including Reporters Without Borders, CJP, and CJFE, agreed on the point that the Iranian government is causing serious threats to their journalists. The state-funded interference includes banning publications, harassing family members of displaced journalists, and bringing the internet to a slow crawl. While the pressure on Iranian journalists has been visibly recognised, the question arises: how much pressure has been exerted and how much has it affected their

psychological mindset? The Results show that the government was involved in arrests, torture, assault, intimidation, and family threats, and the majority of the journalists were scared of working on exclusive stories and stopped working on them.

Hiby et al. (2016) mentioned the data provided by UNESCO and other organisations working for the betterment of media men and revealed that safety matters have become more dangerous during the last decade. Based on the experience of the one hundred journalists and editors, they concluded that it is obvious that the past five years have changed their working environment considerably and for the worse concerning security. The immediate result of this is a reluctance to produce and publish information from conflict zones or to pursue high-risk assignments in regions affected by political tension. Self-censorship is common among journalists and editors, who are particularly vulnerable in their local settings. Reduced security also implies a substantial increase in administration costs for coverage of wars and conflicts worldwide. Altogether, the present findings point towards a threatened press freedom that leads to a degraded quality, and perhaps quantity, of information from contemporary wars and conflicts and their impacts on civil society both at the local and international level. Many journalists are suffering from the after-effects of their work experiences, and the means for safeguarding their mental and physical well-being are deficient.

Baker (2016) highlighted the issue of the safety and imprisonment of al-Jazeera Journalists in Egypt; he applied four theories of the press as a theoretical base and examined the reporting patterns of AJE by using a mixed methodology of content analyses. The results showed that items noted in UNESCO's Safety of Journalists memo were not indicated in the coverage by the presenters but masked under a broader press liberty outline that hung over the case. The research findings also revealed the serious need to discuss the protection of journalists in Egypt and other parts of Africa before things reach their extremes. Sultan (2010) explored the services of Journalists in FATA, how much they were successful in reporting the news about the war on terror in that region of Pakistan, and which types of professional hindrances were on their way to reporting. It concluded that journalists in FATA too want freedom of expression and the right to get access to facts.

Estevez (2010) wrote about the alarming conditions of criminal acts against the press in Mexico City, US. The researchers used a series of intensive interviews with the local press members about the deteriorating situation of increasing deaths of reporters and impunity for the culprits and found that officials failed to implement the rule of law in the city and its inhabitants. Journalists were forced to censor their work; even they were afraid to publish the exclusive stories by their names due to the terror of being victimised. Lumbang, (2009) tried to dig out the reasons and causes of Journalists killings in the Philippines which is considered a free country in South East Asia in terms of the liberty of the press. Yet reporter murder had reached the highest level after the arrival of the democratic regime in 1986. This study showed that nonstop violence against the media workers had

endangered the right of a free press to communicate messages and had also limited the public's right to obtain the news of instant effect. Riddick, et al, (2008), explained the reasons for the killings of media men and explored diverse levels of danger in this field in selected countries of the world. Information was gathered from five online searches about the killings of Journalists from 2002-2006.

Verschingel, (2008) indicated the impotence of news coverage by reporters in conflicts for the survival of democracy. Saul, (2008) demanded the need for social training, education, protection equipment, and health guidance for correspondents before assigning such duties. There are a lot of things that have been mentioned in international laws related to Journalists. Even many European media organisations have introduced special packages for safety measures for their correspondents. Sambrook & Mosdell (2007) reported that a few things are of major concern: the number of Journalists who died, how many were murdered, and what type of inquiries were done to bring the families to justice. The researchers examined the data from the past ten years and used the methodology of interviews conducted with senior Journalists, friends, relatives of those who were killed, and legal experts from various parts of the world. They found that the number of killings was very high during peacetime as compared to the war, and that was increasing day by day. The majority of male and female reporters were targeted because they were throwing light on the evils of society, and the murderers were not recognised due to a lack of investigation.

Balguy-Gallois, (2004) said that there is a need to review the existing laws being formulated at the international level for the security of Journalists from getting victimised while covering war news. The newsmen must be given a free hand if they are not causing any serious damage to humanity by participating with the forces as an ally. Feinstein et al. (2000) examine which type of psychological disorder is faced by war journalists after facing extreme situations of danger and if any kind of effort is made to improve their psychological well-being. They found that war Journalists have more psychiatric difficulties than Journalists who do not respond to war.

Theoretical Framework

The safety of journalists, freedom of the press, and the right to know are the primary duties of the state in the media. Journalists in Pakistan face severe pressure and risk due to the country's perceived safety. Pakistan is considered one of the most unsafe countries for journalists, and it is included in the UNSC plan of action for their protection.

Freedom of expression is guaranteed under Article 19 of the Universal Declaration on Human Rights (UDHR) and Article 19 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR). The right to express oneself freely has been secured in regional treaties such as the European Convention on Human

Rights (ECHR), the American Convention on Human Rights, and the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights.

The constitution of Pakistan states that every citizen has the right to freedom of speech and expression, as well as freedom of the press, subject to reasonable restrictions imposed by law. Article 19(A) also states that every citizen has the right to access information in all matters of public importance, subject to regulation and reasonable restrictions imposed by law.

Libertarian Theory

This study examines theoretically the media's place and task in Pakistani society, where journalists are threatened, harassed, tortured, and shot to death while reporting on militant groups, political parties, the armed forces, and other pressure groups by disclosing their evils and the evils of the society that is covered with lawlessness, corruption, bribery, and other malicious activities.

The libertarian core doctrine begins with the idea of self-ownership. That each person owns himself or herself. So according to the libertarian theory of the press, each person has the absolute right to control his or her own life, body, speech, actions, and honestly acquired property.

"As a result, everyone has a responsibility to respect the rights of others, regardless of their differences. A viewpoint on any political topic can be derived from this starting point that adheres to those principles. While it is acceptable to defend one's rights, it is not acceptable to do so at the expense of another person's rights" (Bergland, 1993).

Research Methodology

The quantitative survey method has been used to collect data through questionnaires from working journalists of different media groups in Lahore. The sample size was 200, selected through simple random sampling. The questionnaire comprises 19 closed-ended questions, and questions 20–6 were measured on a 5-point Likert scale. The purpose was to collect responses from the working journalists of Lahore about reasons for violence against them, the relationship between freedom of expression and violence, and the social effects of violence against journalists. The questionnaire was administered personally, and the journalists were given one hour to complete it.

Research Questions

Q1: What are the reasons for violence against journalists in Pakistan?

Q2: What is the relationship between freedom of expression and Violence?

Q3: Are the journalists finding it difficult to perform their duties well in Pakistan?

Hypotheses

H1: Freedom of Expression leads to Violence against Journalists in Pakistan.

Freedom of Expression does not lead to Violence against Journalists in Pakistan.

H2: Violence is affecting the Professional Commitments of Journalists in Pakistan.

H0: Violence is not affecting the Professional Commitments of Journalists in Pakistan.

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1: Responses regarding news of violence against journalists and their feelings

News of violence	Sometimes	39%	Often	31.5%	Very often	29.5%	100%
Feeling about the news of violence	Become careful%	52%	Get fearful	23%	Unaffected	25%	100%

Most journalists sometimes come across news about violence against their co-workers; indeed, journalists often report on violence as part of their job, and it can be said that news about violence against journalists is not unusual for the journalist community. When they hear about such incidents, most of them become more careful in their work.

Table 2: Reasons for violence against journalists and the threats they received while performing their duty

Reasons	Injustice	23%	External Pressures	24%	blackmailing	18%	Following Objectivity	20%	Personal interests	15%	100%
Threats	Pressure groups	19%	Religious groups	14%	Political parties	18%	Agencies	19%	Terrorists	30%	100%

The table shows that objectivity, personal interests, blackmailing, pressure from external sources, and injustice are the reasons for violence against journalists in Pakistan. It concludes that pressure from external sources is the main reason, while objectivity, personal interests, and injustice are also reasons in some or other context. Journalists believe that most threats come from terrorists.

Table 3: Relationship between Freedom of Expression and Violence

	Yes	No	Total
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Freedom of expression	71%	29%	100%
Following objectivity in danger	56%	44%	100%

The table shows that (58) of Journalists have the opinion that freedom of expression by Journalists does not lead to violence against them, while (142) of the respondents have the opinion that freedom of expression by Journalists does lead to violence against them. So, it has been proven from the outcome that freedom of expression leads to violence against journalists. The table depicts that about (87) of Journalists say that Journalists do not follow objectivity in an environment of fear and pressure, and about (113) of the respondents say that Journalists do follow objectivity in the presence of fear and pressure. Hence, a large number of journalists follow objectivity irrespective of any kind of fear or pressure.

Table 4. *In Pakistan, it is difficult for journalists to effectively carry out their tasks.*

	Yes	No	Total
Is Pakistan dangerous for journalists?	65%	35%	100%
Journalists quit their job due to fear.	64 %	36%	100%
Violence force journalists to censor their work.	57%	43%	100%

Table 3 shows that the maximum number of respondents consider Pakistan a dangerous country for journalists. They face threats of different kinds and have to practise self-censorship to avoid endangering themselves and their families. Journalists were of the view that freedom of expression, lack of justice, and failure to track the culprits are the reasons for violence against journalists; about 14% (27) of the journalists thought that freedom of expression was the reason, and about 40% (79) of the Journalists had the opinion that lack of justice was the reason; 15% (30) of the journalists considered that failure to track the culprits was the reason for violence against Journalists in Pakistan; and 31% (64) believed that all of them were the reasons.

Table 5: *Violence against Journalists and its social impact*

	Yes	No	Total
Do you face violence?	60%	40%	100%
Reporting violence to the government or their organization	00 (124 out of 200 didn't reply to this question)	39%	39%
Self-defence training	84%	16%	100%

The table shows that 46 (124) of the Journalists said that they did not report incidents of violence to the government or their organisation, whereas 76 said that they did report incidents of violence to the government or their organisation. A total of 124 out of 200 samples replied to the answer to this question, while 76 did not. indicates that 33 of the Journalists replied that there is no need for self-defence training for media personnel, and 167 of them emphasised that yes, there is a need for self-defence training for media personnel.

Figure-1

The above figure shows that (8) of the Journalists said that they hardly faced violence during their career, and (63) of them replied that they occasionally faced violence during their career. 42 replied that they often face violence during their careers, and 11 of them said that they frequently face violence during their careers. A total of 124 respondents out of 200 replied to the answer to his question, while 76 of them did not reply because they chose option "no" in the previous question about facing violence in performing their duties. The respondents have the view that they have been subjected to violence in their lives occasionally or often.

Table 6: news of Violence and its social impact

News of violence and its social impact	Not at all	To less extent	To some extent	To great extent	Total
	30%	24%	28%	20%	100%

The table shows that (59) of the Journalists have the opinion that the news of violence does not create any impact on their social lives; (47) of them say that news of violence on Journalists affects their social lives to a lesser extent; (55) of the respondents say that it does create an impact to some extent; and (39) of the journalists say that news of violence on fellow Journalists does create an impact on their social lives to a great extent.

Figure:2

The data concludes that (35) of Journalists said that threats do not leave any negative impact on the social life of journalists; (36) of them have the opinion that threats create an impact on social life to a lesser extent; (84) of them believed that threats have a moderate impact on social life to some extent; and (45) believed that threats do create a great impact on the social life of Journalists. The answers obtained from the question asked indicate mixed opinions about the impact of violence on the social life of journalists, but overall, they indicate that violence does have a negative impact on their social lives.

Figure:3

This figure indicates that about 49% of the respondents agreed that the news of violence against other journalists does not affect their professional commitments, and about 39% said that the news of violence does affect their commitment to a lesser extent. (76) respondents said that news of violence against journalists does create an impact on their commitment to their profession to some extent, and (36) of the Journalists have this thought that news of violence does create an impact to a great extent.

Table: 7. Freedom of expression enjoyed by journalists

Freedom of expression	Always	Sometimes	Do not enjoy	Do enjoy
	9%	37%	30%	24%

The table shows that most of the time freedom of expression is enjoyed by the journalists in Pakistan.

Table 8: Levels of Agreement on the following Questions

	Strongly disagreed	Disagreed	Neutral	Strongly agreed	Agreed
Violence increased due to the war against terrorism	6%	10%	20%	46%	19%
Freedom of expression and threats	3%	11%	20.5%	50%	15.5%
Pakistani journalists living in Fear	5.5%	19.5	32%	33%	10%
Journalists are forced to disguise	9.5%	29%	26%	26%	9.5%
Security and journalists	13.5	24.5	14.5	21%	26.5%
Credibility of journalists	8%	14%	23.5%	36.5%	18%

The table shows that (11) of the journalists strongly disagreed that violence against Journalists has increased ever since Pakistan indulged in the war against terrorism; (19) of them disagreed with this; (40) remained neutral; (92) agreed that violence against Journalists has increased ever since Pakistan has indulged in the war against terrorism; and (38) strongly agreed. It also depicts that (6) of the journalists strongly disagreed that Journalists are threatened if they practise freedom of expression, (22) of them disagreed, (41) of them remained neutral, and (100) agreed that Journalists are threatened if they practise freedom of expression, whereas (31) of them strongly agreed. It has been proven from the answers of respondents that a maximum number of them agreed that journalists are threatened if they practise freedom of expression. The majority of journalists are of the opinion that journalists

are living in fear. It also shows that (19) of the journalists strongly disagreed that Pakistani Journalists are forced to hide and disguise themselves due to fear of violence, (58) of them disagreed, (52) remained neutral, and (52) agreed that Pakistani Journalists are forced to hide and disguise themselves due to fear of violence, whereas (19) of them strongly agreed. Journalists do want security from the government.

The survey results indicate that the majority of Journalists have encountered violence in their careers, with a smaller percentage often hearing about such incidents. The majority of Journalists become more cautious after hearing about violence, feeling more confident when they hear about it. The majority of Journalists believe that freedom of expression leads to violence against them, while a small number of them feel fearful after hearing such news. The majority of Journalists believe that news of violence against other Journalists has an impact on their professional commitment, while a small number of Journalists believe that violence against fellow Journalists does not. The majority of Journalists believe that fear and pressure from external sources are the main reasons for violence against Journalists in Pakistan, while a small number of Journalists believe that objectivity, personal interest, blackmailing, pressure from external sources, and injustice are not the main reasons. The majority of Journalists believe that Pakistan is a dangerous country for Journalists, with a small number of them stating that freedom of expression is the main reason for labelling the country as dangerous. Most Journalists believe that threats received from terrorist groups, pressure groups, security agencies, and religious groups are the main reasons for violence against Journalists in Pakistan. The majority of Journalists do not quit their jobs due to fear of violence, while a small number do. Most Journalists face violence while performing their duties, while a small number do not. Most Journalists report incidents of violence to authorities or their organisations, while a small number do not. A large number of Journalists are in favour of self-defence training, while a small number are against it. The majority of Journalists believe that the credibility of Journalists is affected by violence and threats, while a small number strongly disagree. The majority of Journalists agree that violence against media men has increased since Pakistan has become involved in the war against terrorism, while a small number strongly disagree. They also agree that Journalists are threatened if they practise freedom of expression, while a small number strongly disagree. The study also shows that a large number of Journalists believe that Pakistani Journalists are living in growing fear of violence, while a small number strongly disagree. Most Journalists disagree that media personnel are forced to disguise themselves, while a small number strongly disagree.

In conclusion, the survey results reveal that the majority of Journalists in Pakistan are aware of the potential dangers of violence and threats to their credibility. The government should provide security to Journalists, while a small number of Journalists remain sceptical of the government's role in addressing these issues.

Hypothesis Testing & Results

Chi-square was applied to assess the results of the survey after inserting them in SPSS. The following conclusions have been drawn.

Hypothesis 1: Freedom of Expression leads towards Violence against Journalists in Pakistan.

H0: Freedom of Expression does not lead towards Violence against Journalists in Pakistan.

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.150 ^a	4	.128
Likelihood Ratio	6.737	4	.150
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.631	1	.105
N of Valid Cases	200		

Hypothesis 1 was tested and the value of Pearson Chi-square as shown in the above table is 0.128 which is greater than the significant value of 0.05, hence this hypothesis is rejected. Whereas the Null hypothesis has been accepted.

Hypothesis 2 Violence is affecting the Professional Commitments of Journalists in Pakistan.

H0: Violence is not affecting the Professional Commitments of Journalists in Pakistan.

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	23.560 ^a	12	.023
Likelihood Ratio	23.508	12	.024
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.043	1	.044
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 3 cells (15.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.88.

Hypothesis 2 was tested and the value of Pearson chi-square as shown in the above table is .023 which is lesser than the significant value of 0.05, hence this hypothesis is accepted. The null hypothesis has been rejected.

Conclusion

The press is the fourth pillar of the state and plays a crucial role in keeping the masses informed. Journalists play a significant role in handling society's issues, and their work is essential for maintaining stability. However, violence against journalists in Pakistan has been reported, with working conditions often unfavourable for them. The study aimed to analyse the impact of violence on Pakistani journalists' professional commitments and dedication. Two hypotheses were tested. The results showed that violence does impact their devotion and dedication to their profession, leading to self-censorship and a decline in their credibility. Despite the fear of violence, journalists continue to face challenges and struggle for survival.

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APPENDIX

Survey Questionnaire for Journalists

Impact of Violence on the Professional Commitments of Pakistani Journalists

QUESTIONNAIRE

I am a student of MS Mass Communication at Lahore College for Women University. I am conducting a research thesis titled “Impact of Violence on the Professional Commitments of Pakistani Journalists”. This research is only for academic purposes and the information will only be used for study purposes.

Name: _____ Gender: _____

Age: _____ Organization: _____

Working as: _____

Journalistic Experience: _____

Please tick the chosen options:

Q1. Do you come across any news of violence against journalists?

(a) Very often (b) often (c) sometimes

Q2. When you come across any news of violence against journalists how does it make you feel?

(a) You become more confident (b) You become careful and cautious (c) You get fearful

(d) You remain unaffected

Reasons for Violence against Journalists

Q. 3. What are the reasons for violence against journalists in our country?

(a) Objectivity (b) Personal interests (c) blackmailing (d) Pressure from any external sources regarding reporting of any news (e) injustice (f) none of them (g) all of them

Q4. In your opinion most journalists receive threats from

(a) Political parties/ politicians (b) Terrorists/ terrorist organizations or groups

(c) Law enforcement agencies (d) any religious groups (e) other pressure groups

Freedom of expression and violence

Q.5. Freedom of expression by journalists leads to violence against them

(a) Yes (b) No

Q.6. Do you think that freedom of expression is enjoyed by Journalists in Pakistan?

(a) Yes (b) No (Sometimes) (Always)

Q.7. The news of any incident of violence against other journalists affects your professional commitment.

(a) To great extent (b) To some extent (c) To less extent (d) Not at all

Q.8. News of incidents of violence against fellow journalists affects your social life.

(a) To great extent (b) To some extent (c) To less extent (d) Not at all

Q.9. Journalists follow objectivity in an environment of fear and pressure.

(a) Yes (b) No

Hard job

Q.10. Do you think that **Pakistan** is a dangerous country for journalists?

(a) Yes (b) No

Q.11. If yes, why

(a) Failure to track the culprits (b) lack of justice (c) freedom of expression
d) All of them

Q.12. Do you think that journalists quit their jobs due to fear of violence?

(a) Yes (b) No

Q.13. Violence forces journalists to censor their work.

(a) Yes (b) No (c) Sometimes

Violence and social issues

Q.14. Threats leave a negative impact on the social life of journalists.

(a) To great extent (b) To some extent (c) To less extent (d) Not at all

Q.15. Have you ever thought about quitting your profession due to fear of violence?

(a) Yes (b) No

Q.16. Have you ever been subjected to any form of violence while performing your professional duties?

(a) Yes (b) No

Q.17. If yes, how many times you have faced violence during your career?

(a) Frequently (b) Often (c) Occasionally (d) Hardly

Q.18. Did you report such an incident to the government or your organization/ employer?

(a) Yes (b) No

Q.19. Do you think self-defence training should be given to media personnel?

(a) Yes (b) No

Q.20. Tick the appropriate option:

(SDA-strongly disagree, DA-disagree, N-neutral, A -agree, SA-strongly agree)

Statement	SD	D	N	A	SA
	A	A			

1.	The credibility of journalists is affected due to violence and threats					
2.	Violence against journalists has increased ever since Pakistan indulged in the war against terrorism					
3.	Do you think that journalists are threatened if they practice freedom of expression					
4.	Are the Pakistani journalists living in growing fear of violence					
5.	Pakistani journalists are forced to hide and disguise themselves due to fear of violence					
6.	Our government should provide security to journalists due to the risk of violence against them					